

New eurytomid parasitoids of bark beetles in pine plantations in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains, Bulgaria

Sevdalin Belilov¹, Anelia Stojanova², Georgi Georgiev³

(1) Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, weasevdo@gmail.com ✉

(2) Department of Zoology, Faculty of Biology, Plovdiv University Paisii Hilendarski, 24 Tsar Assen Street, 4000 Plovdiv, Bulgaria, stanelia@uni-plovdiv.bg ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0842-1446> 🔗

(3) [Corresponding author] Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, ggeorgiev.fri@gmail.com ✉; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5703-2597> 🔗

Abstract: In 2020, five eurytomid species were found for first time on bark beetles in *Pinus sylvestris* plantations in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains in Bulgaria: *Eurytoma afra* Boheman, 1836, *Eurytoma arctica* Thomson, 1875, *Eurytoma morio* Boheman, 1836, *Eurytoma* sp.1 and *Eurytoma* sp.2. One of them, *E. arctica* is a new species for the Bulgarian fauna. The parasitoids were reared from stem and branch samples infested by *Ips acuminatus*, *Pityogenes bistridentatus*, *Pityophthorus pityographus*, *Tomicus piniperda* and *T. minor*. All host-parasitoid associations are new for Bulgaria. In parasitoid complex, the most abundant species was *E. morio* (75.9%), followed by *E. arctica* (13.8%), *Eurytoma* sp. (6.9%) and *E. afra* (3.4%). The parasitism of the hosts varied between 2.6% (*E. afra* on *I. acuminatus*, *P. bistridentatus* and *P. pityographus*) and 33.3% (*E. morio* on *I. acuminatus*).

Keywords: Bulgaria, Eurytomidae, new records, parasitoids, *Pinus sylvestris*, Scolytinae

Introduction

The bark beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) are one of the most dangerous taxonomic groups of insects on forest vegetation. In coniferous forests, species of the genera *Dendroctonus*, *Ips*, *Tomicus*, etc. are the most destructive (Cognato, 2015; Lieutier et al., 2015; Smith & Hulcr, 2015). Their number is regulated by various natural factors, including a numerous complex of parasitoids from different hymenopteran (Hymenoptera) and dipteran (Diptera) families (Kenis et al., 2004; Wegensteiner et al., 2015).

In the last sixty-seventy years, extensive anti-erosion plantations of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) and Austrian pine (*Pinus nigra* Arn.) have been created in the lower and middle forest belts in Bulgaria (Popov et al., 2018). In these plantations, strong attacks by bark beetles have recently been observed (Mirchev et al., 2016).

In Bulgaria, the parasitoids of bark beetles are not well studied and there is only fragmentary knowledge about individual hosts. In most studies, species from the family Braconidae have been reported (Tschorbadjiev, 1930; Mirchev et al., 2002; Balevski & Georgiev, 2003; Georgiev & Takov, 2005; Doychev & Balevski, 2006; Doychev et al., 2016; Belilov & Georgiev, 2023). Parasitoids from only two families of Chalcidoidea have been reported in separate publications: Heydenidae (Belilov et al., 2023) and Pteromalidae (Georgiev & Takov, 2005; Georgiev & Stojanova, 2006; Doychev et al., 2016; Belilov et al., 2023). Currently, however, no parasitoids from the Eurytomidae family are known on bark beetles in the country.

The present study reports new eurytomid parasitoids (Hymenoptera: Eurytomidae) of bark beetles in pine plantations in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains in Bulgaria.

Fig. 1. Studied localities in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains.

Material and methods

The studies on parasitoids of bark beetles were conducted in 2020 in two sample plots in plantations of *Pinus sylvestris* L. in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains on the territory of State Forestry Enterprise Elin Pelin and State Game Enterprise Aramliets. They are situated in the region of Krushovitsa Village (N 42.615944, E 23.784333, 651 m a.s.l.) and Golema Rakovitsa Village (N 42.590466, E 23.657520, 697 m a.s.l.) (Fig. 1).

The samples (cuttings of stems and branches of approximate length 30–35 cm and diameter 5–30 cm) of trees attacked by bark beetles were collected on 5 June 2020.

The biological material was transported to the Forest Research Institute in Sofia where each cutting was kept in a separate photoelector at room temperature (18–22°C). The samples were observed weekly for the emergence of adult hosts or parasitoids. The emerged parasitoids were stored in ethanol.

In this study, the percentage of parasitism of bark beetles was calculated based on the number of

emerged hosts and parasitoids in the different photoelector samples.

The parasitoids were examined under an Olympus SZ51 stereomicroscope and photographed using a Leica EZ4 W stereomicroscope supplied with a WiFi CMOS still camera. The photos were processed by Zerene Stacker and were subsequently edited by manually combining adjusting and cleaning in Adobe Photoshop.

The emerged bark beetles were identified using the keys of Karaman (1971) and Grüne (1979), and the parasitoids – using the key of Delvare et al. (2014).

The bark beetles were deposited in the entomological collection of the Forest Research Institute in Sofia, and the parasitoids – in the entomological collection of the Plovdiv University Paisii Hilendarski.

Results

Five eurytomid parasitoids (Hymenoptera: Eurytomidae) were reared from the tree samples: *Eurytoma*

Table 1. Characteristics of eurytomid parasitoids of bark beetles in Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains.

Species	Locality	Host	Emergence period	Parasitoid number			Parasitism, %	Share, %
				♂♂	♀♀	Σ		
<i>Eurytoma afra</i>	Krushovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i> <i>P. bistridentatus</i> <i>P. pityographus</i>	30.07.2020	1	—	1	2.6	3,5
<i>Eurytoma arctica</i>	G. Rakovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i>	02.08.2020	—	1	1	6.3	13.8
	G. Rakovitsa	<i>T. piniperda</i> <i>T. minor</i>	02.08.2020	1	—	1	3.7	
	Krushovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i> <i>P. bistridentatus</i> <i>P. pityographus</i>	02.08.2020	2	—	2	5.6	
<i>Eurytoma morio</i>	G. Rakovitsa	<i>Ips acuminatus</i>	19.07–02.08.2020	5	2	7	33.3	75.9
	Krushovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i> <i>P. bistridentatus</i> <i>P. pityographus</i>	05.06–02.08.2020	1	8	9	25.0	
	Krushovitsa	<i>Ips acuminatus</i>	23.07–02.08.2020	—	6	6	4.8	
<i>Eurytoma</i> sp.1	Krushovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i> <i>P. bistridentatus</i> <i>P. pityographus</i>	30.07.2020	1	—	1	2.5	3,4
<i>Eurytoma</i> sp.2	Krushovitsa	<i>I. acuminatus</i> <i>P. bistridentatus</i> <i>P. pityographus</i>	27.07.2020	1	—	1	2.5	3,4
Total				12	17	29		100.0

afra Boheman, 1836, *Eurytoma arctica* Thomson, 1875, *Eurytoma morio* Boheman, 1836, *Eurytoma* sp.1 and *Eurytoma* sp.2 (Table 1).

Eurytoma arctica (Fig. 2A, B) is a new species for Bulgarian fauna. In our work, we reared two male specimens belonging to different species – *Eurytoma* sp.1 (Fig. 2C) and *Eurytoma* sp.2 (Fig. 2D). Reliable species identification of *Eurytoma* by single male specimens is very difficult, even more so in the absence of recent keys based on males of the known species. *Eurytoma* sp.1 is close to *E. arctica* in wing venation but has a short petiole. *Eurytoma* sp.2 is related to *E. afra* by wing venation and petiole size, but the specimen lacks antennae for reliable identification.

The parasitoids were reared from stem samples infested by *Ips acuminatus* (Gyllenhal, 1827), *Pityogenes bistridentatus* (Eichhoff, 1878), *Pityophthorus pityographus* (Ratzeburg, 1837), *Tomicus piniperda* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Tomicus minor* (Hartig, 1834). All host-parasitoid associations are new for Bulgaria.

In parasitoid complex, the most abundant species was *E. morio* (75.9%), followed by *E. arctica* (13.8%), *E. afra* (3.5%), *Eurytoma* sp.1 and *Eurytoma* sp.2 (3.4%).

The parasitism of the hosts varied between 2.6% (*E. afra* on *I. acuminatus*, *P. bistridentatus* and *P. pityographus*) and 33.3% (*E. morio* on *I. acuminatus*).

Discussion

Eurytoma afra is widely distributed in Europe, South Siberia, Canada and USA as a parasitoid of bark beetles (Coleoptera: Curculionidae, Scolytinae) (including *Ips* and *Pityogenes* genera) and gall midges (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) (Noyes, 2019). In Bulgaria, it was reported only once as a parasitoid of *Dasineura saliciperda* (Dufour, 1841) (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) (Georgiev & Stojanova, 2003).

The new species for the Bulgarian fauna, *E. arctica* is a Transpalaeartic species distributed in

Fig. 2. Reared parasitoids: A – *Eurytoma arctica* (female); B – *Eurytoma arctica* (male); C – *Eurytoma* sp.1 (male); D – *Eurytoma* sp.2 (male).

Europe, Iran, Siberia and China (Shaanxi Province) (Noyes, 2019). According to the database, it is a primary parasitoid associated with curculionid hosts (*Magdalis*, *Pissodes*, *Dryocoetes*, *Ernoporus*, *Hylesinus*, *Hylurgops*, *Ips*, *Orthotomicus*, *Pityogenes*, *Scolytus*, *Tomicus*) and a hyperparasitoid of Braconidae (*Coeloides*) and Pteromalidae (*Rhopalicus*). The bark beetles found in this study (*Ips acuminatus*, *Tomicus piniperda* and *T. minor*) belong to the primary host range of *E. arctica* (Kenis et al., 2004).

The Palaearctic *E. morio* is a primary-secondary parasitoid with wide range of hosts from different coleopteran, lepidopteran and hymenopteran families: Cerambycidae (*Pogonochaerus*, *Tetrops*), Curculionidae (*Chaetoptelius*, *Magdalis*, *Pissodes*, *Carphoborus*, *Dryocoetes*, *Hylesinus*, *Ips*, *Leperesinus*, *Orthotomicus*, *Phloeosinus*, *Phloeotribus*, *Pityogenes*,

Polygraphus, *Scolytus*, *Tomicus*, *Xyleborus*), Gelechiidae (*Exoteleia*), Pieridae (*Aporia*), Braconidae (*Coeloides*) and Pteromalidae (*Cheiropachus*) (Noyes, 2019). In Bulgaria, it was reported (syn. *Eurytoma ischioxanthos* Ratzeburg, 1844) as a parasitoid of *Scolytus rugulosus* (Müller, 1818) (Tschorbadjiev, 1930).

In this study, the euritomid parasitoids caused relatively low host mortality (no more than 33.3%). In the same area (Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mountains), however, the mortality of bark beetles caused by parasitoids of Pteromalidae and Heydenidae in some cases reaches very high values: 89.6% in *P. bistridentatus*, 90.5% in *I. acuminatus*, and 91.7% in *T. piniperda* and *T. minor* (Belilov et al., 2023).

In conclusion, it should be noted that the discovery of a new parasitoid enriches euritomid

fauna of Bulgaria, and the establishing of new host-parasite associations expands knowledge about the ecology of bark beetles in Bulgaria.

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